

"Machine Learning Advances in 2020"

**International Journal of Computer Science &
Information Technology (IJCSIT)**

ISSN: 0975-3826(online); 0975-4660 (Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit.html>

ENSEMBLE LEARNING MODEL FOR SCREENING AUTISM IN CHILDREN

Mofleh Al Diabat¹ and Najah Al-Shanableh²

^{1,2}Department of Computer Science, Al Albayt University, Al Mafraq- Jordan

ABSTRACT

Autistic Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurological condition associated with communication, repetitive, and social challenges. ASD screening is the process of detecting potential autistic traits in individuals using tests conducted by a medical professional, a caregiver, or a parent. These tests often contain large numbers of items to be covered by the user and they generate a score based on scoring functions designed by psychologists and behavioural scientists. Potential technologies that may improve the reliability and accuracy of ASD tests are Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning. This paper presents a new framework for ASD screening based on Ensembles Learning called Ensemble Classification for Autism Screening (ECAS). ECAS employs a powerful learning method that considers constructing multiple classifiers from historical cases and controls and then utilizes these classifiers to predict autistic traits in test instances. ECAS performance has been measured on a real dataset related to cases and controls of children and using different Machine Learning techniques. The results revealed that ECAS was able to generate better classifiers from the children dataset than the other Machine Learning methods considered in regard to levels of sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy.

KEYWORDS

Artificial Neural Network, Autism Screening, Classification, Ensemble Learners, Predictive Models, Machine Learning

Full Text: http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2019_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Pennington, M. L., Cullinan, D., & Southern, L. B. (2014). [Defining autism: variability in state education agency definitions of and evaluations for Autism Spectrum Disorders](#). Autism Research and Treatment, 1-8.
- [2] Thabtah, F. (2018A) [Machine learning in autistic spectrum disorder behavioral research: A review and ways forward](#). Informatics for Health and Social Care 43 (2), 1-20.
- [3] Chu, K. C., Huang, H. J., & Huang, Y. S. (2016). Machine learning approach for distinction of ADHD and OSA. In *Advances in Social Networks Analysis and Mining (ASONAM), 2016 IEEE/ACM International Conference on* (pp. 1044-1049). IEEE.
- [4] Lopez Marcano, J. L. (2016). Classification of ADHD and non-ADHD Using AR Models and Machine Learning Algorithms (Doctoral dissertation, Virginia Tech).
- [5] Duda M., Ma R., Haber N., Wall D.P. (2016). Use of machine learning for behavioral distinction of autism and ADHD. *Translational Psychiatry* (9(6), 732.
- [6] Bone, D., Goodwin, M. S., Black, M. P., Lee, C.-C., Audhkhasi, K., & Narayanan, S. (2016). [Applying machine learning to facilitate autism diagnostics: pitfalls and promises](#). Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders, 1121–1136.
- [7] Thabtah F., Kamalov F., Rajab K. (2018) [A new computational intelligence approach to detect autistic features for autism screening](#). International Journal of Medical Informatics, Volume 117, pp. 112-124.
- [8] Abbas, H., Garberson, F., Glover, E., & Wall, D. P. (2018). [Machine learning approach for early detection of autism by combining questionnaire and home video screening](#). Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association, 25(8), 1000-1007. doi:10.1093/jamia/ocy039
- [9] Altay, O., & Ulas, M. (2018). Prediction of the Autism Spectrum Disorder Diagnosis with Linear Discriminant Analysis Classifier and K-Nearest Neighbor in Children. 2018 6th International Symposium on Digital Forensic and Security (ISDFS). Antalya, Turkey: IEEE. doi:10.1109/ISDFS.2018.8355354
- [10] Ravindranath, V., & Ra, S. (2018). A machine learning based approach to classify Autism with optimum behaviour sets. International Journal of Engineering and Technology. doi:10.14419/ijet.v7i3.18.14907
- [11] Thabtah F., Peebles D. (2019) A new machine learning model based on induction of rules for autism detection. Health Informatics Journal, 1460458218824711.
- [12] R. M. Mohammad, F. Thabtah and L. McCluskey, "[Predicting Phishing Websites using Neural Network trained with Back-Propagation](#)," in ICAI, Las Vegas, 2013-C.

- [13] R. M. Mohammad, F. Thabtah and L. McCluskey, "[Predicting phishing websites based on self-structuring neural network](#)," Neural Computing and Applications, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 443-458, 2013-B.
- [14] S. Madhusmita, S. K. Dash, S. Dash and A. Mohapatra, "[An approach for iris plant classification using neural network](#)," International Journal on Soft Computing , vol. 3, no. 1, 2012.
- [15] F. Amato, A. López, E. M. Peña-Méndez, P. Vañhara, A. Hampf and J. Havel, "[Artificial neural networks in medical diagnosis](#)," Journal of Applied Biomedicine, vol. 11, no. 2, p. 47–58, 2013.
- [16] M. Riley, J. Karl and T. Chris, "[A Study of Early Stopping, Ensembling, and Patchworking for Cascade Correlation Neural Networks](#)," IAENG International Journal of Applied Mathematics, vol. 40, no. 4, pp. 307-316, 2010.
- [17] Thabtah, F. (2018). [An accessible and efficient autism screening method for behavioural data and predictive analyses](#). Health Informatics Journal, 1-17. doi:10.1177/1460458218796636
- [18] Thabtah F., ASDTests. A mobile App for ASD Screening, (2017) (Accessed 14 March 2019), www.asdtests.com
- [19] Ventola, P., Kleinman, J., Pandey, J., Barton, M., Allen, S., Green, J., . . . Fein, D. (2006). Agreement among four diagnostic instruments for autism spectrum disorders in toddlers. Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders, 839-47.
- [20] Vllasaliu, L., Jensen, K., Hoss, S., Landenberger, M., Menze, M., Schutz, M., . . . Freitag, C. M. (2016). [Diagnostic instruments for autism spectrum disorder \(ASD\)](#). Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews, 1-27.
- [21] Thabtah F. (2017) Autism Spectrum Disorder Tools: Machin Learning Adaptation and DSM-5 Fulfillment: An Investigative Study. Proceedings of the 2017 International Conference on Medical and Health Informatics (ICMHI 2017), pp. 1-6. Taichung, Taiwan. ACM.
- [22] Baron-Cohen, S. (2001). Take the AQ test. Journal of Autism and developmental disorders, 5-17.
- [23] Allison, C., Baron-Cohen, S., Charman, T., Wheelwright, S., Richler, J., Pasco, G., & Brayne, C. (2008). [The Q-CHAT \(quantitative checklist for autism in toddlers\): a normally distributed quantitative measure of autistic traits at 18–24 months of age: preliminary report](#). Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders, 1414–1425.

- [24] Witten, I. and Frank, E. (2005). Data Mining: Practical Machine Learning Tools and Techniques.
- [25] Freund, Y. and Schapire, R.E., (1997) [A Decision-Theoretic Generalization of On-Line Learning and an Application to Boosting](#). Journal of Computer and System Sciences, 55(1), p.119–139.
- [26] Quinlan, J. (1986). Induction of Decision Trees. Mach. Learn. 1(1): 81-106.
- [27] Fusaroli, R., Lambrechts, A., Bang, D., Bowler, D. M., & Gaigg, S. B. (2017, March). “Is voice a marker for Autism spectrum disorder? A systematic review and meta-analysis”. *Autism Research*, 10, 384-407. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/aur.1678>
- [28] Tariq, Q., Daniels, J., Schwartz, J. N., Washington, P., Kalantarian, H., & Wall, D. P. (2018, November 27). Mobile detection of autism through machine learning on home video: A development and prospective validation study. *PLoS Med*, 15(11). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1002705>
- [29] Satu, S., Sathi, F. F., Arifen, S., & Ali, H. (January 2019). Early Detection of Autism by Extracting Features:A Case Study in Bangladesh. *International Conference on Robotics, Electrical and Signal Processing Techniques*. Dhaka. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330383730_Early_Detection_of_Autism_by_Extracting_Features_A_Case_Study_in_Bangladesh
- [30] Wong , V., Hui , L., Lee , W., Leung , L., Ho , P., Lau, W., . . . Chung, B. (2004). A modified screening tool for autism (Checklist for Autism in Toddlers [CHAT-23]) for Chinese children. *Pediatrics*, 166-76.
- [31] Hall, M., Frank, E., Holmes, G., Pfahringer, B., Reutemann, P., & Witten, I. H. (2009). The WEKA data mining software: an update. *ACM SIGKDD explorations newsletter*, 11(1), 10-18.
- [32] Quinlan, J. (1993). *C4.5: Programs for machine learning*. San Mateo, CA: Morgan Kaufmann.
- [33] BreimanL. (2001) Random forests. Mach. Learning, 45(1):5-32, 2001. 1300
- [34] Friedman, N., Geiger, D. and Goldszmidt, M. (1997) Bayesian Network Classifiers. Machine Learning - Special issue on learning with probabilistic representations, 29(2-3), pp.131-63.
- [35] Bi, X.-a., Wang, Y., Shu, Q., Sun, Q., & Xu, Q. (2018). [Classification of Autism Spectrum Disorder Using Random Support Vector Machine Cluster](#). *Frontiers in genetics*, 9(18). doi:10.3389/fgene.2018.00018

- [36] Lord, C., Risi, S., Lambrecht, L., Cook, E. H., Leventhal, B. L., DiLavore, P. C., & Pickles, A. (2000). [The Autism diagnostic observation schedule-generic: a standard measure of social and communication deficits associated with the spectrum of autism](#). *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 205-223.
- [37] Schopler, E., Van Bourgondien, M. E., Wellman, J., & Love, S. R. (1980). [Toward objective classification of childhood autism: childhood autism rating scale \(cars\)](#). *Autism DevDisord*, 91–103.
- [38] Allison, C., Auyeung, B., & Baron-Cohen, S. (2012). [Toward brief “red flags” for autism screening: the short autism spectrum quotient and the short quantitative checklist in 1,000 cases and 3,000 controls](#). *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 51(2), 202-212.
- [39] Frank, E., and Witten, I. (1998) [Generating accurate rule sets without global optimisation](#). *Proceedings of the Fifteenth International Conference on Machine Learning*, (p. . 144–151). Madison, Wisconsin.
- [40] Cohen, W. W. (1995). [Fast effective rule induction](#). In *Machine Learning Proceedings 1995 (pp. 115-123)*. Morgan Kaufmann.
- [41] Freund, Y., & Schapire, R. E. (1999). [Large margin classification using the perceptron algorithm](#). *Machine learning*, 37(3), 277-296.
- [42] Abdelhamid, N., Thabtah, F., and Abdel-jaber, H. (2017). Phishing detection: A recent intelligent machine learning comparison based on models content and features. 2017 IEEE International Conference on Intelligence and Security Informatics (ISI), pp. 72-77. 2017/7/22, Beijing, China.
- [43] Abdelhamid N., Ayesh A., Thabtah F. (2013) Classification. *Proceedings of the International conference on AI '2013*, pp. 687-695. LV, USA. Associative Classification Mining for Website Phishing
- [44] Thabtah F., Hadi W., Abdelhamid N., Issa A. (2011) Prediction Phase in Associative Classification. *Journal of Knowledge Engineering and Software Engineering*. Volume: 21, Issue: 6(2011) pp. 855-876. WorldScinet.
- [45] Thabtah F., Mahmood Q., McCluskey L., Abdel-jaber H (2010). A new Classification based on Association Algorithm. *Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, Vol 9, No. 1, pp. 55-64. World Scientific.
- [46] Thabtah F., Cowling P., and Peng Y. (2006): Multiple Label Classification Rules Approach. *Journal of Knowledge and Information System*. Volume 9:109-129. Springer.

INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM CLASSIFICATION USING DIFFERENT MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS ON KDD-99 AND NSL-KDD DATASETS - A REVIEW PAPER

Ravipati Rama Devi¹ and Munther Abualkibash²

**¹Department of Computer Science, Eastern Michigan University,
Ypsilanti, Michigan, USA**

**²School of Information Security and Applied Computing, Eastern Michigan University,
Ypsilanti, Michigan, USA**

ABSTRACT

Intrusion Detection System (IDS) has been an effective way to achieve higher security in detecting malicious activities for the past couple of years. Anomaly detection is an intrusion detection system. Current anomaly detection is often associated with high false alarm rates and only moderate accuracy and detection rates because it's unable to detect all types of attacks correctly. An experiment is carried out to evaluate the performance of the different machine learning algorithms using KDD-99 Cup and NSL-KDD datasets. Results show which approach has performed better in term of accuracy, detection rate with reasonable false alarm rate.

..

KEYWORDS

Intrusion Detection System, KDD-99 cup, NSL-KDD, Machine learning algorithms.

Full Text: <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V11N3/11319ijcsit06.pdf>

REFERENCES

- [1] “DARPA98 attack description and schedule,” <https://www.ll.mit.edu/ideval/docs/attacks.html>, 1998, retrieved December 15, 2016.
- [2] L. Breiman, J. H. Friedman, R. A. Olshen, and C. J. Stone, Classification and Regression Trees, 1984.
- [3] D. A. Cieslak and N. V. Chawla, “A [framework for monitoring classifiers’ performance: when and why failure occurs?](#)” Knowledge and Information Systems, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 83–108, 2009.
- [4] M. Fugate and J. R. Gattiker, “[Anomaly detection enhanced classification in computer intrusion detection.](#)” in Pattern Recognition with Support Vector Machines, vol. 2388, 2002, pp. 186–197.
- [5] M. Tavallae, E. Bagheri, W. Lu, and A. A. Ghorbani, “[A detailed analysis of the KDD CUP 99 data set.](#)” in IEEE Symposium on Computational Intelligence for Security and Defense Applications, CISDA 2009, 2009.
- [6] J. McHugh, “[Testing Intrusion detection systems: a critique of the 1998 and 1999 DARPA intrusion detection system evaluations as performed by Lincoln Laboratory.](#)” ACM Transactions on Information and System Security, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 262–294, 2000.
- [7] S. Sung, A.H. Mukkamala. “ ”. [In Proceedings of the Symposium on Applications and the Internet \(SAINT\)](#), pp. 209–216. IEEE.
- [8] H. Kayacik, A. Zincir-Heywood and M. Heywood. “[Selecting features for intrusion detection: A feature relevance analysis on KDD 99 intrusion detection datasets](#)”. In Proceedings of the Third Annual Conference on Privacy, Security and Trust (PST). 2005.
- [9] C. Lee, S. Shin and J. Chung. “Network intrusion detection through genetic feature selection”. In Seventh ACIS International Conference on Software Engineering, Artificial Intelligence, Networking, and Parallel/Distributed Computing (SNPD), pp. 109–114. IEEE Computer Society, 2006.
- [10] H. Zhang and J.Su., “[Naive Bayes for optimal ranking](#)”, Journal of Experimental and Theoretical Artificial Intelligence. 2008, 20: 79-93.
- [11] Z. Muda, W. Yassin, M.N. Sulaiman, N.I. Udzir, “[Intrusion Detection based on K-Means Clustering and Naïve Bayes Classification](#)” 2011 7th International Conference on IT in Asia (CITA)”.
[12] Weiming Hu, Steve Maybank, “[AdaBoost-Based Algorithm for Network Intrusion Detection](#)”. In IEEE transaction on systems, MAN, and CYBERNETICS, APRIL 2008.

IMAGE GENERATION WITH GANS-BASED TECHNIQUES: A SURVEY

Shirin Nasr Esfahani¹and Shahram Latifi²

¹Department of Computer Science, UNLV, Las Vegas, USA

²Department of Electrical & Computer Eng., UNLV, Las Vegas, USA

ABSTRACT

In recent years, frameworks that employ Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) have achieved immense results for various applications in many fields especially those related to image generation both due to their ability to create highly realistic and sharp images as well as train on huge data sets. However, successfully training GANs are notoriously difficult task in case if high resolution images are required. In this article, we discuss five applicable and fascinating areas for image synthesis based on the state-of-the-art GANs techniques including Text-to-Image-Synthesis, Image-to-Image-Translation, Face Manipulation, 3D Image Synthesis and DeepMasterPrints. We provide a detailed review of current GANs-based image generation models with their advantages and disadvantages. The results of the publications in each section show the GANs based algorithms ARE growing fast and their constant improvement, whether in the same field or in others, will solve complicated image generation tasks in the future.

KEYWORDS

Conditional Generative Adversarial Networks (cGANs), DeepMasterPrints, Face Manipulation, Text-to-Image Synthesis, 3D GAN

Full Text: <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V11N5/11519ijcsit03.pdf>

REFERENCES

- [1] Goodfellow, I. J., Pouget-Abadie, J., Mirza, M., Xu, B., Warde-Farley, D., Ozair, S., Courville, A., & Bengio, Y. (2014) “Generative adversarial nets”, Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 27 (NIPS 2014), Montreal, Canada.
- [2] Frey, B. J. (1998) “[Graphical models for machine learning and digital communication](#)”, MIT press.
- [3] Doersch, C. (2016) “[Tutorial on variational autoencoders](#)”, arXiv preprint arXiv:1606.05908.
- [4] M. Mirza & S. Osindero (2014) “Conditional generative adversarial nets”, arXiv:1411.1784v1.
- [5] Sh.Nasr Esfahani, & Sh. Latifi (2019) “[A Survey of State-of-the-Art GAN-based Approaches to ImageSynthesis](#)”, 9th International Conference on Computer Science, Engineering and Applications (CCSEA 2019), Toronto, Canada, pp. 63-76.
- [6] S. Reed, Z. Akata, X. Yan, L. Logeswaran, B. Schiele & H. Lee (2016) “[Generative adversarial text to image synthesis](#)”, International Conference on Machine Learning, New York, USA, pp. 1060-1069.
- [7] A. Radford, L. Metz & S. Chintala (2016) “[Unsupervised representation learning with deep convolutional generative adversarial networks](#)”, 4th International Conference of Learning Representations (ICLR 2016), San Juan, Puerto Rico.
- [8] S. Reed, Z. Akata, S. Mohan, S. Tenka, B. Schiele & H. Lee (2016) “[Learning what and where to draw](#)”, Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, pp. 217–225.
- [9] S. Zhu, S. Fidler, R. Urtasun, D. Lin & C. L. Chen (2017) “[Be your own prada: Fashion synthesis with structural coherence](#)”, International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV 2017), Venice, Italy, pp. 1680-1688.
- [10] S. Sharma, D. Suhubdy, V. Michalski, S. E. Kahou & Y. Bengio (2018) “[ChatPainter: Improving text to image generation using dialogue](#)”, 6th International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR 2018 Workshop), Vancouver, Canada.
- [11] Z. Zhang, Y. Xie & L. Yang (2018) “[Photographic text-to-image synthesis with a hierarchically-nested adversarial network](#)”, Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR 2018), Salt Lake City, USA, pp. 6199-6208
- [12] M. Cha, Y. Gwon & H. T. Kung (2017) “[Adversarial nets with perceptual losses for text-to-image synthesis](#)”, International Workshop on Machine Learning for Signal Processing (MLSP 2017), Tokyo, Japan, pp. 1- 6.
- [13] H. Dong, S. Yu, C. Wu & Y. Guo (2017) “[Semantic image synthesis via adversarial learning](#)”, International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV 2017), Venice, Italy, pp. 5706-5714.
- [14] H. Zhang, T. Xu, H. Li, S. Zhang, X. Wang, X. Huang, and D. Metaxas (2017) “[Stackgan: Text to photo-realistic image synthesis with stacked generative adversarial networks](#)”, International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV 2017), Venice, Italy, pp. 5907-5915.

- [15] S. Hong, D. Yang, J. Choi & H. Lee (2018) “[Inferring semantic layout for hierarchical text-to-image synthesis](#)”, Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR 2018), Salt Lake City, USA, pp. 7986-7994.
- [16] Y. Li, M. R. Min, Di. Shen, D. Carlson, and L. Carin (2018) “[Video generation from text](#)”, 14th Artificial Intelligence and Interactive Digital Entertainment Conference (AIIDE 2018), Edmonton, Canada.
- [17] J. Chen, Y. Shen, J. Gao, J. Liu & X. Liu (2017) “Language-based image editing with recurrent attentive models”, The IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR 2018), Salt Lake City, USA, pp. 8721-8729.
- [18] A. Dash, J. C. B. Gamboa, S. Ahmed, M. Liwicki & M. Z. Afzal (2017) “[TAC-GAN-Text conditioned auxiliary classifier](#)”, arXiv preprint arXiv: 1703.06412, 2017.
- [19] A. Odena, C. Olah & J. Shlens (2017) “[Conditional image synthesis with auxiliary classifier GANs](#),” Proceeding of 34th International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML 2017), Sydney, Australia.
- [20] H. Zhang, I. Goodfellow, D. Metaxas & A. Odena (2018) “[Self-attention, generative adversarial networks](#)”, arXiv preprint arXiv:1805.08318, 2018.
- [21] T. Xu, P. Zhang, Q. Huang, H. Zhang, Z. Gan, X. Huang & X. He (2018) “AttnGAN: Fine-grained text to image generation with attentional generative adversarial networks”, The IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR 2018), Salt Lake City, USA, pp. 1316-1324.
- [22] T. Salimans, I. J. Goodfellow, W. Zaremba, V. Cheung, A. Radford & X. Chen (2016) “[Improved techniques for training GANs](#)”, Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 29 (NIPS 2016), Barcelona, Spain.
- [23] P. Isola, J.-Y. Zhu, T. Park & A. A. Efros (2017) “Image-to-image translation with conditional adversarial networks”, The IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR 2017), Honolulu, Hawaii, USA, pp. 1125-1134.
- [24] J.-Y. Zhu, T. Park, P. Isola & A. A. Efros (2017) “Unpaired Image-to-Image Translation using Cycle-Consistent”, The IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV2017), Venice, Italy, pp. 2223-2232.
- [25] M.-Y. Liu & O. Tuzel (2016) “[Coupled generative adversarial networks](#)”, 2016 Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NIPS 2016), Barcelona, Spain, pp. 469–477.
- [26] J. Donahue, P. Krähenbühl & T. Darrell (2016) “[Adversarial feature learning](#)”, 4th International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR 2016), San Juan, Puerto Rico.
- [27] V. Dumoulin, I. Belghazi, B. Poole, A. Lamb, M. Arjovsky, O. Mastropietro & A. Courville (2017) “[Adversarially learned inference](#)”, 5th International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR 2017), Toulon, France.
- [28] M. Cordts, M. Omran, S. Ramos, T. Rehfeld, M. Enzweiler, R. Benenson, U. Franke, S. Roth, & B. Schiele (2016) “The cityscapes dataset for semantic urban scene understanding”, The IEEE

- Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR 2016), Las Vegas, USA, pp. 3213-3223.
- [29] Q. Chen & V. Koltun (2017) “Photographic image synthesis with cascaded refinement networks”, IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV 2107), Venice, Italy, pp. 1520–1529.
- [30] T.-C. Wang, M.-Y. Liu, J.-Y. Zhu, A. Tao, J. Kautz & B. Catanzaro (2018) “High-resolution image synthesis and semantic manipulation with conditional GANs”, The IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR 2018), Salt Lake City, USA, pp. 8798-8807.
- [31] G. Lample, N. Zeghidour, N. Usunier, A. Bordes, L. Denoyer & M. Ranzato (2017) “[Fader networks: Manipulating images by sliding attributes](#)”, Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 30 (NIPS 2017), Long Beach, USA.
- [32] D. Michelsanti & Z.-H. Tan (2017) “[Conditional generative adversarial networks for speech enhancement and noise-robust speaker verification](#)”, Proceeding of Interspeech, pp. 2008–2012.
- [33] Z. Akhtar, D. Dasgupta, B. Baerjee (2019) “[Face Authenticity: An Overview of Face Manipulation Generation, Detection and Recognition](#)”, International Conference on Communication and Information Processing (ICCIP-2019)”, Pune, India.
- [34] R. Sun, C. Huang, J. Shi, L. Ma (2018) “[Mask-aware photorealistic face attribute manipulation](#)”, arXiv preprint arXiv:1804.08882, 2018.
- [35] Antipov, M. Baccouche & J.-L. Dugelay (2017) “Face aging with conditional generative adversarial networks”, IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP 2017), pp.2089 – 2093.
- [36] R. H. Byrd, P. Lu, J. Nocedal & C. Zhu (1995) “A limited memory algorithm for bound constrained optimization”, SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 1190–1208, 1995.
- [37] Z. Wang, X. Tang, W. Luo & S. Gao (2018) “Face aging with identity preserved conditional generative adversarial networks”, Proceeding IEEE Conference Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, CVPR 2018), Salt Lake City, USA, pp. 7939–7947.
- [38] G. Antipov, M. Baccouche & J.-L. Dugelay (2017) “Boosting cross-age face verification via generative age normalization”, International Joint Conference on Biometrics (IJCB 2017), Denver, USA, pp. 17.
- [39] Z. Zhang, Y. Song & H. Qi (2017) “Age progression/regression by conditional adversarial auto encoder”, IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR 2017), Honolulu, USA, pp. 4352 – 4360.
- [40] G. Perarnau, J. van de Weijer, B. Raducanu and J.M. Alvarez (2016) “[Invertible conditional gans for image editing](#)”, arXiv preprint arXiv:1611.06355, 2016.
- [41] M. Li, W. Zuo and D. Zhang (2016) “[Deep identity-aware transfer of facial attributes](#)”, arXiv preprint arXiv:1610.05586, 2016.
- [42] Y. Choi, M. Choi, and M. Kim (2018) “Stargan: Unified generative adversarial networks for multi-domain image-to-image translation”, Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR2018), Salt Lake City, USA, pp. 8789–8797.

- [43] W. Chen, X. Xie, X. Jia and L. Shen (2018) “Texture deformation based generative adversarial networks for face editing”, arXiv preprint arXiv:1812.09832, 2018.
- [44] W. Shen and R. Liu (2017) “Learning residual images for face attribute manipulation”, Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR 2017), Honolulu, Hawaii, USA, pp. 4030–4038.
- [45] H. Yang, D. Huang, Y. Wang and A. K. Jain (2017) “[Learning face age progression: A pyramid architecture of gans](#)”, arXiv preprint arXiv:1711.10352, 2017.
- [46] H. Arian (2019) “FaceApp: How Neural Networks can do Wonders”, Noteworthy - The Journal Blog, <https://blog.usejournal.com/tagged/faceapp>.
- [47] J. Wu, C. Zhang, T. Xue, W. T. Freeman & J. B. Tenenbaum (2016) “[Learning a probabilistic of object shapes via 3d generative-adversarial modeling](#)”, In Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 29 (NIPS 2016), Barcelona, Spain.
- [48] J. Wu, Y. Wang, T. Xue, X. Sun, B. Freeman & J. Tenenbaum (2017) “[Marnet: 3d shape reconstruction via 2.5 d sketches](#)”, Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, Long Beach, USA, pp. 540–550.
- [49] W. Wang, Q. Huang, S. You, C. Yang & U. Neumann (2017) “Shape inpainting using 3d generative adversarial network and recurrent convolutional networks”, The IEEE international Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV 2017), Venice, Italy, pp. 2298-2306.
- [50] E. J. Smith & D. Meger (2017) “[Improved adversarial systems for 3d object generation and reconstruction](#)”, first Annual Conference on Robot Learning, Mountain View, USA, pp. 87–96.
- [51] P. Achlioptas, O. Diamanti, I. Mitliagkas & L. Guibas (2018) “[Learning representations and generative models for 3d point clouds](#)”, 6th International Conference on Learning Representations, Vancouver, Canada.
- [52] X. Sun, J. Wu, X. Zhang, Z. Zhang, C. Zhang, T. Xue, J. B. Tenenbaum & W. T. Freeman (2018) “Pix3d: Dataset and methods for single-image 3d shape modeling”, IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR 2018), Salt Lake City, USA, pp. 2974-2983.
- [53] D. Maturana & S. Scherer (2015) “VoxNet: A 3D Convolutional Neural Network for real-time object recognition”, 2015 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), Hamburg, Germany, pp. 922 – 928.
- [54] B. Shi, S. Bai, Z. Zhou & X. Bai (2015) “DeepPano: Deep Panoramic Representation for 3-D Shape Recognition”, IEEE Signal Processing Letters, vol. 22(12), pp. 2339 – 2343.
- [55] A. Brock, T. Lim, J. Ritchie & N. Weston (2016) “[Generative and discriminative voxel modeling with convolutional neural networks](#)”, arXiv:1608.04236.
- [56] A. Roy, N. Memon, and A. Ross (2017) “MasterPrint: Exploring the vulnerability of partial fingerprint-based authentication systems”, IEEE Trans. Inf. Forensics Security, vol. 12, no. 9, pp. 2013–2025.

- [57] P. Bontrager, A. Roy, J. Togelius, N. Memon and A. Ross (2018)“DeepMasterPrints: Generating MasterPrintsforDictionaryAttacks via Latent Variable Evolution”, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1705.07386.pdf>
- [58] M. Arjovsky, S.Chintala, and L. Bottou(2017), “ Wasserstein generative adversarial networks”, InProceedingsof the 34th International Conference on Machine Learning(ICML2017), Sydney, Australia,Vol. 70, pp. 214–223.

AUTHOR

Shirin Nasr Esfahani received her M.S. degree in computer science – scientific computation from Sharif University of technology, Tehran- Iran. She is currently a Ph.D. candidate in computer science, University of Nevada, Las Vegas (UNLV). Her fields of interest include, hyper spectral image processing, neural networks, deep learning and data mining.

Shahram Latifi received the Master of Science and the PhD degrees both in Electrical and Computer Engineering from Louisiana State University, Baton Rouge, in 1986 and 1989, respectively. He is currently a Professor of Electrical Engineering at the University of Nevada, Las Vegas.

DETECTION OF FAKE ACCOUNTS IN INSTAGRAM USING MACHINE LEARNING

Ananya Dey¹, Hamsashree Reddy², Manjistha Dey³ and Niharika Sinha⁴

¹National Institute of Technology, Tiruchirappalli, India

²PES University, Bangalore, India

³RV College of Engineering, Bangalore, India

⁴Manipal Institute of Technology, Karnataka, India

ABSTRACT

With the advent of the Internet and social media, while hundreds of people have benefitted from the vast sources of information available, there has been an enormous increase in the rise of cyber-crimes, particularly targeted towards women. According to a 2019 report in the [4] Economics Times, India has witnessed a 457% rise in cybercrime in the five year span between 2011 and 2016. Most speculate that this is due to impact of social media such as Facebook, Instagram and Twitter on our daily lives. While these definitely help in creating a sound social network, creation of user accounts in these sites usually needs just an email-id. A real life person can create multiple fake IDs and hence impostors can easily be made. Unlike the real world scenario where multiple rules and regulations are imposed to identify oneself in a unique manner (for example while issuing one's passport or driver's license), in the virtual world of social media, admission does not require any such checks. In this paper, we study the different accounts of Instagram, in particular and try to assess an account as fake or real using Machine Learning techniques namely Logistic Regression and Random Forest Algorithm.

KEYWORDS

Logistic Regression, Random Forest Algorithm, median imputation, Maximum likelihood estimation, k cross validation, overfitting, out of bag data, recall, identity theft, Angler phishing.

Full Text: <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V11N5/11519ijcsit07.pdf>

REFERENCES

- [1] Indira Sen, Anupama Aggarwal, Shiven Mian. 2018. "[Worth its Weight in Likes: Towards Detecting Fake Likes on Instagram](#)". In ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management.
- [2] Shalinda Adikari, Kaushik Dutta. 2014. "[Identifying Fake Profiles In LinkedIn](#)". In Pacific Asia Conference on Information Systems.
- [3] Aleksei Romanov, Alexander Semenov, Oleksiy Mazhelis and Jari Veijalainen. 2017. "[Detection of Fake Profiles in Social Media](#)". In 13th International Conference on Web Information Systems and Technologies.
- [4] <https://telecom.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/india-saw-457-rise-in-cybercrime-in-five-years-study/67455224>
- [5] Todor Mihaylov, Preslav Nakov. 2016. "[Hunting for Troll Comments in News Community Forums](#)". In Association for Computational Linguistics.
- [6] ML-cheatsheet.readthedocs.io. (2019). Logistic Regression — ML Cheatsheet documentation. [Online] Available at: https://ml-cheatsheet.readthedocs.io/en/latest/logistic_regression.html#binarylogistic-regression [Accessed 10 Jun. 2019].
- [7] 3. Schoonjans, F. (2019). ROC curve analysis with MedCalc. [Online] MedCalc. Available at: <https://www.medcalc.org/manual/roc-curves.php> [Accessed 10 Jun. 2019].
- [8] Kietzmann, J.H., Hermkens, K., McCarthy, I.P., Silvestre, B.S., 2011. Social media? Get serious! Understanding the functional building blocks of social media. Bus.Horiz., SPECIAL ISSUE: SOCIAL MEDIA 54, 241251. doi:10.1016/j.bushor.2011.01.005.
- [9] Krombholz, K., Hobel, H., Huber, M., Weippl, E., 2015. [Advanced Social Engineering Attacks](#). J Inf SecurAppl 22, 113–122. doi:10.1016/j.jisa.2014.09.005.